

UTILITY OF THE "ALBUMINOID AMMONIA" VALUE IN THE
ANALYSIS OF FOODSTUFFS. PART II. ANALYSIS OF
FRUIT JUICES, SQUASHES AND CORDIALS*

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The determination of albuminoid ammoniacal nitrogen was found to be a very helpful sorting test in the examination of soft fruit drinks like fruit juices, squashes and cordials, just as for vinegar¹. This figure helps in distinguishing synthetic from genuine products containing fruit juices. The albuminoid ammoniacal nitrogen contents of some samples of different pure fruit juices were determined and maximum, minimum and average values with standard deviations were worked out. Also, there is a broad relationship between the figures for total and albuminoid ammoniacal nitrogens, by which the *approximate* value of total nitrogen, and hence of total proteins of these fruit drinks, can be calculated from their albuminoid nitrogen.

Samples of fruits were collected from the local (Calcutta) market. In cases of fruits obtainable almost throughout the year, e.g. lime, samples were collected and examined in the different seasons. In case of orange, the two principal varieties, namely, the "Nagpur" and "Dorjeeling", which appear in the local market, were collected. The "Mossambic" orange was treated as ~~separate~~ separate fruit. Mango appears in a great many varieties like, *gulapkhos*, *begunfulli*, *langra*, *fazli*, *bombai (himsagar)*, *madrasi*, etc. All the varieties of mango were analysed. In case of apple, the *Kashmir* and the imported fruit from abroad were examined. Both the green and black grapes were collected for ~~examination~~ examination.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The method for determining albuminoid ammoniacal nitrogen of fruit drinks has been described in the Analyst². To counteract the reducing action of sugars present in these products, the method was modified by adding an excess of solid potassium permanganate in addition to the alkaline permanganate reagent in the second distillation. Results summarised in Table I are expressed in parts per million (w/w).

*A short note on the subject appeared in the Analyst, 1953, 78, 681. Reproduced here by permission of the Society for Analytical Chemists, England.

TABLE I

Fruit juice.	No. of samples.	Albuminoid ammoniacal nitrogen*				Total nitrogen				AAN/TN	
		Max.	Min.	Av.	S. D.	Max.	Min.	Av.	S. D.	Av.	S. D.
Lime (pure undiluted)	18	456	294	358	46.97	1090	800	966	73.23	0.35	0.043
Orange	30	750	337	521	97.12	1575	807	1183	190.47	0.44	0.028
Tomato	15	570	333	412	54.36	1200	800	936	101.62	0.44	0.029
Mango	37	1000	290	615	228.21	2000	672	1283	434.20	0.48	0.029
Grape	20	570	250	365	96.71	1140	600	780	187.90	0.47	0.025
Apple	20	450	130	267	106.02	1125	365	744	239.86	0.35	0.030
Pineapple	14	520	260	359	79.95	1036	540	731	161.09	0.49	0.015
Orange (mossambic variety)	8	700	520	604	64.20	1530	1162	1301	127.29	0.46	0.010
Pomegranate	8	370	270	315	28.72	740	504	578	81.50	0.55	0.061

AAN stands for albuminoid ammoniacal nitrogen.

TN total nitrogen.

S. D. standard deviation.

DISCUSSION

From the above figures it will be seen that the natural variation in the total and albuminoid nitrogens of lime juice is not large, but the variations in case of orange, mango, grape, apple and pineapple juices, are much larger, the largest having been observed in the case of apple and mango juice. Larger variation in these fruits appears to be mainly due to varietal difference. This is not unexpected, because there are so many varieties of mango fruits, mango juice having the highest average value of albuminoid ammoniacal nitrogen while apple juice, the lowest.

The last column in Table I shows the relation between the total and the albuminoid nitrogens. The average values for the ratio "AAN/TN" are recorded with the standard deviations. It will be noticed that these ratios are somewhat close to each other in case of orange, tomato, mango, grape and pineapple juices, with a range of 0.44 to 0.49. Those for the lemon and apple juices are on the low side, and for pomegranate juice on the high side. For estimating the *approximate* protein contents of these fruit juices therefore, the time-consuming Kjeldahl method for determining total nitrogen may be successfully replaced by the easier albuminoid nitrogen determination. Results of analysis of authentic and artificial squashes, cordials and crushes are shown below.

TABLE II

Type of soft drink.	Range of albuminoid ammoniacal nitrogen p.p.m. (w/w).		Range of total nitrogen p.p.m. (w/w).	
Authentic products :				
Lime squash (7 samples)	72	to 150	205	to 420
Orange squash (7 samples)	100	to 220	200	to 616
Lime juice cordial (7 samples)	80	to 100	185	to 315
Artificial or adulterated products :				
Squashes and cordial (10 samples)	Nil	to 45	7	to 90
Lemon and orange crushes (9 samples)	Nil	to 24	7	to 63

It will be noticed that there is a large difference between the albuminoid nitrogens of authentic and spurious products. At the worst, some of the synthetic products did not contain any natural fruit juice, and were made up of sugar syrup, citric acid, a little colouring and flavouring matter. These yielded no albuminoid ammoniacal nitrogen at all. The albuminoid nitrogens of authentic squashes and cordials varied according to the type and amount of fruit juice present.

The reason for using 4 g. of solid potassium permanganate in the determination of albuminoid ammoniacal nitrogen of soft fruit drinks.—In order to find out the optimum amount of solid potassium permanganate required to counteract the reducing action of sugars in soft drinks, experiment was carried out by adding varying amounts of permanganate, i.e. 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 g., in addition to the 50 ml. of the permanganate reagent in the second distillation. For this purpose, the soft drink with the maximum sugar content possible, i.e. 45 to 50%, was taken, since the optimum amount of permanganate required for such concentrations would also suffice for a syrup of lower sugar concentration. Results are shown in Table III.

TABLE III

Variation in the value of albuminoid NH₃-N with varying amounts of solid KMnO₄ (Syrup used was of 35% sugar concentration)

Amount of KMnO ₄ added in addition to the 50 ml. of alkaline permanganate reagent.	Albuminoid NH ₃ -N of the soft drinks, p.p.m. (w/w).	Remarks.
1 g.	...	Colour of permanganate discharged
2	140	Do
3	335	Colour of permanganate very slightly discharged
4	335	Colour of permanganate <i>not</i> discharged
5	335	Do

Therefore, making a little allowance, the amount of 4 g. of solid potassium permanganate was accepted, although 3 g. was just sufficient. To keep uniformity of procedure this amount (4 g.) was used for all soft drinks and fruit juices, although all of them by no means contained high percentage of sugar.

S U M M A R Y

It has been shown that in the examination of soft drinks such as, fruit juices, squashes, cordials, crushes etc., the figure for the albuminoid ammoniacal nitrogen is of great value in detecting purely synthetic products. The procedure for the determination of albuminoid ammonia in these products was slightly modified to counteract the reducing action of sugars present.

As a first step total and albuminoid nitrogens of nine different types of undiluted pure fruit juices were determined and average value with standard deviation for each type of fruit juice was worked out. Also, there exists a

broad relationship between the figures for total and albuminoid nitrogens, by which the total nitrogen and hence the total proteins can be calculated *approximately* from the albuminoid nitrogen.

There is a marked difference between the albuminoid nitrogens of authentic squashes and cordials, and those of artificial products containing very little fruit juices, so that this determination can be used as a rapid sorting test in routine analysis. The method is far more simple and much less time-consuming than the long Kjeldahl digestion method for total nitrogen.

Author's note :

Results of analysis of three samples of lime juice, fifteen of orange juice, thirteen of grape juice, sixteen of apple juice, two of mango juice, eight of pomegranate juice and the average figures for total and albuminoid ammoniacal nitrogens with standard deviations in Table I, Table III, major portions of the introduction, discussion and summary, and the results of nine artificial¹ fruit crushes in Table II, did not appear in the Analyst.

R E F E R E N C E S

1. Mitra, *Analyst*, 1953, **78**, 499.
2. Mitra & Roy, *ibid.*, 1953, **78**, 681.